

Value creation in place management: The relevance of Service Providers

Author Name: Marcello Sansone

Abstract— This paper identifies the place, such as natural or artificial spaces able to play important roles in the development process of the quality of life of analyzed places, in a dynamic perspective of catalysts for economic interests, for sociological surveys, for interpretive marketing schemes, for environmental implications. Over time, the attention to the relationship between sustainable and potential development of territory and to the importance of the service providers have acquired increasing significance in marketing and place development studies.

The importance of the service provider is grounded in the assumption of two relevant logic categories -*Basic and Relevant Service Provider*- characterizing their role in the strategy of value creation and place development: in the reflections about place management, conducted with some international research units, the aim is to highlight the central role of service providers in the development of sustainable places also through the support of the analysis of cases.

Index Terms— Place management, place marketing, service provider, value creation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The document “*Europe 2020 Strategy. A strategy for smart and inclusive growth*” declares a dynamic view of the social market projected into the twenty-first century, with the simultaneous identification of three priorities:

1. smart growth, developing an economy based on knowledge and innovation;
2. promoting a more resource efficient, greener and more competitive economy, that doesn't necessarily have a public guide but a governance able to incentivize a real renewal of industrial districts or declining places – *for example the transformation of certain territories from industrial pure places to local systems of knowledge or high-integration of both*;
3. cooperative governance models; in this sense the importance of services becomes essential in the relationship between business development and places growth.

Two important logical categories of service providers - *basic service providers and relevant service providers*- impact on the importance of Services in the sustainable development of the places. Some literature's contributions indicate the categories of service providers needed to identify a distinctive mix that increase the opportunities for value creation in a Clear marketing strategy. The Relevant Service Provider identify some specific services that determine the arise of distinctive characteristics of places, a new ability to compete and raise the place value, a strong and enduring collaboration between stakeholders often in opposition over territorial policies, a systemic vision of the area; in this work retail is included in the macro-area of Services for final consumption. The Relevant Service Provider emerges as

distinctive factors of the area and contribute significantly to its positioning; starting from the post-industrial approach (Bell, 1974), the intangible and knowledge economies, has allowed the overcoming of neo-industrial (Gershuny,1978) that identified the central role of tangible production in the place economies, through the generation of services.

The objective of this paper is to describe the strategic role of service providers in the development of places: in particular in the first part it will be explained a literature review regarding the role and the evolution of services in place management. Then it focuses on how the services can actually have an influence on places and how they can improve life of the primary and secondary stakeholders. In the last part, consistent with the theory above, it focuses on some empirical cases -*national and international*- in which it is possible to find the strategic role of service providers in the creation of clear and identifiable place positioning.

II. THE EVOLUTION OF THE ROLE OF SERVICES IN PLACE ECONOMIES AND MANAGEMENT

Scientific reflections of marketing management not always improve the role of Services Industry in Place Management. Effectively, the position of Services Industry has often been opposed by tradeoff between consolidation of existing methods and new elements in the progression of the place systems.

Although the place management models and the company management models are different, it's necessary to tend toward the management of the places as Companies; indeed the strategic cooperation between stakeholders caused a repositioning that reenhanced a place area otherwise declining.

In the sixties, reference literature ascribed to Service Providers a limited capability to make money: it evidences an extreme customization capability of services to the detriment of the creation of relevant economies of significant scale. It underlines the derangement attributed to the service's role en rapport to the industries that could cause a loss of expertise (Baumol, 1967).

Subsequently other authors have proposed a negative view with respect to the contribution of Service Providers to the development of the economy, arguing that the multiplication of service's activities affected the rising costs of industrial products; more attention to the services would generate higher costs for manufacturing industry (Goldfinger, 1996; Thurow, 1987; Rullani, 1988).

The contributions reported are part of a thought that pays for , on one hand , of the limits that result from an excessive conceptual opposition between materiality of production and immateriality of services, on the other hand serves the consequences of the difficulty to determinate methods of productivity of the different sections of services.

In parallel with the cited critical literature contribution, starting from the 80's some lines of thought are developed: they consider positively the contribution of services compared to their role in

the economy and notably for the territory. (Baumol, 2002) wrote about the importance of service providers emphasizing its validity and positivity for economic and territorial development: in particular, the author identifies services as value added to the productive sector. That is because among other things, these are continually being enhanced by the development of new technologies; the paths towards the dematerialization encouraged an evolutionary cycle of new technologies that have contributed significantly to the economic and industrial improvement (Levitt, 1976; Rullani 1995; Gronroos, 1998).

Proceeding with the analyses of the changing role of the services and, more generally, of the tertiary sector it must be paid attention on a specific phase of the 80's: the companies provided free services in exchange of purchase of products. In the 90's some companies began to distribute free products in order to sell services over the long term like maintenance, management and training (Sahalman, 1999).

Since the late 90's the decisive role of knowledge-based economy, the de-materialization and globalization, have further enhanced the services sector and multiplied the value of new technologies (Rifkin, 2000). Particularly, the development of ICT technologies has fostered the exchange of opportunities; the abatement of distances, together with the increased affordability of most modern services. As for the bid, companies have benefited from the opportunity to enhance the interactions with the micro and macro-environment with all the negative and positive resulting features which in any case have favored a more appropriate technological evolution at all levels.

In this regard you can refer to the parallel that develops between the expansion of outsourcing in enterprises¹, the internet diffusion and the development of highly specialized service providers; specifically, Del Monte (2001) emphasizes that, thanks to the network, many businesses rely on external partners for the supply of goods and services different from its own core business.

Moreover, the changing role of the services comes to a sort of passing of the service itself. As several authors argue, the economy of mere service has left the field to the experiential economy. In its new context, the value for the customer – extremely picky – is created by the company offering experiences rather than goods and services: experiences represent proposals that differ profoundly from services at least as much as the services are different from goods (Pandav and Forlani, 2002). Starting from these service definitions, which, also using different approaches, converge toward notions of immateriality and multiformity of the phenomenon difficult to replicate identically, we come to an analysis of service providers in the development of territorial realities, which will obtain benefit if organized in the perspective of place marketing management.

III. THE RELEVANCE OF SERVICE PROVIDER IN PLACE MANAGEMENT

The service industry is complex in its forms as there are different interpretations for the identification of specific sectors; when referring to the exponential development of ICT we are talking about high-tech service industry (Momigliano and Siniscalco, 1970) to denote the homogeneous group of services provided by high-tech companies, mainly addressed to BtoB, which define new areas of development of services. In this work, it was decided to borrow certain categories of service providers, that help to determine the competitiveness of territories with

particular reference to cities, from the classification of Gadrey and Martinelli (2000).

Specifically, services are classified into four macro-areas in order to highlight their value in relation to the development of the territory from the perspective of place marketing management. The synergistic contribution of macro-service areas identified will determine the place positioning, the competitive potential, the international difficulties and, finally, the development of the territory. The immateriality of services is linked to the performance of service providers, depending on the quality of the economic environment, will lead to different performances and results.

Table 1 shows the macro-areas of service integrated with service providers of reference.

TABLE 1

<p><i>Social services</i> (public administration, defense, justice, security, civil protection, public health, basic and higher education, social assistance, public welfare);</p> <p><i>Services for end consumer</i> (modern retail - trade and personal services - tourist services);</p> <p><i>Infrastructure services</i> (land, sea and air transport, communications and telecommunications);</p> <p><i>Business services</i> (ICT, finance, insurance, real estate services, research and spreading of knowledge, advanced training, other business services)</p>

Gadrey Martinelli (2000)

Service providers contribute to the competitive growth of urban economy and of manufacturing system by increasing the creation and development of knowledge, innovation, technology and the proper economic and financial structure of the territory; they integrate with the surrounding territories and, over time, become active and passive stakeholders of territory that, increasingly, bases its development on the stability of service industry and it repositions the place features on the knowledge economies.

In this work, the term Service Provider, refers to all the service providers in general who insist on the territories; the term Relevant Service Provider, in a place in process of upgrading and positioning, indicates service providers able to differentiate themselves from the generality and able to emerge in the market, for competitive skills, income generation, market share, positioning, ability to provide services and to assert its relevance in spatial realities different from the original.

The “ Relevant” service providers that emerge from the territory may be the result of a mix of values, cultural heritage, skills and knowledge characteristics of the land itself, or, they may simply affect the local community through the dissemination of best practices and knowledge. The services contribute to the positioning and re-positioning of entire geographical areas, with particular reference to the cities through the development of an intangible model based on values and with the emergence of the knowledge economy, with globalization and outsourcing in manufacturing.

Several factors have favored, in recent years, especially in Italy, the development of organizational forms and managerial stakeholders, often in coordination and not in opposition to the public authority¹: the innovation of industry sector in the urban areas; the appeal of new formats and concepts of sales and administration with indirect purpose of increasing the aesthetic value of real estate and urban well-being; the trend of local communities to prefer “urban” gathering places” in the process of consumption of goods and satisfaction of expanded needs; the vital role of cities and city centers in particular in the rediscovery of the value of art and cultural initiatives.

In line with this approach, the retail service providers in some cities can be considered Relevant Service Provider, for their competitiveness and their importance in the place economy: innovative and shared procedures to manage the competitiveness can originate only through the systematization of ideas, plans and activities in a strategic marketing plan (Ancaroni and Valdani, 2000).

In this phase of work often emerges the fragmentation of decision-making bodies, the cultural heterogeneity of regional stakeholders, various points of view of a place, the disagreement of strategic aims, the lack of a territorial collective intentionality (Gatti and Schillaci, 2011). These factors do not generate any form of land value and spread of knowledge models replicable and measurable even in the urban area, resulting, conversely, the conditions for an impoverishment of the urban fabric.

A clear positioning of the various territorial sub-sites and an effective communication of the “local supply”, as inseparable core of goods and services oriented to consumers and to users of utility, arise ex ante from an overall strategy -framework strategy- inclusive programs for tourism marketing, cultural heritage, urban marketing, attraction of inward investment, development of endogenous activities, on the basis of rigorous and analytical activities of place segmentation.

Policy makers should create a place brand only after a careful and scientific analysis of identity, values, characteristics, strengths and weakness, degree of territorial cohesion and aptitude to collective intentionality. It could be proved that, in practice, as the institutional actors often appoint resources and capabilities to create a brand logically disconnected from the conceptual framework, this is a cost and not an effective use of resources for the development of places.

The place marketing management “reads and interprets” the places, prioritizing their same segmentation, the critical evaluation of their current status, the positioning and /or repositioning, the size of the urban centers, the importance of manufacturing capacity for the conversion of entire areas in patterns of knowledge and intangible resources: for example, places developed around the large manufacturing enterprise and its satellite activities, supported by subsidies and facilities of various kinds, which decline rapidly as soon as the large company decided to move production elsewhere by choice

¹ In Italy there are a lot of example: the experiences of the Town Centre Management, the company for the development of tourism in the collective mode, the association between public and private through agencies for development of the territory according to shared projects by economic actors of the territory and the public bodies. Abroad experiences are varied, especially when referring to the city. An example is the experience of Northern Europe related to TCM (Town Centre Management) and the BID (Business Improvement District).

related to lower cost of factors of production, causing moreover the desertification of entire economic and social areas.

The strategic role of private service providers in support of normal daily activities of residents, is even more evident when you consider that urban space is characterized as “the densest, the most productive, the most complex of spaces”, according to various parameters – index of construction industry, residents, stakeholders, economic activities, different skills, creativity, knowledge, structure of employment.

The ability to attract and the sustainable development have a strategic role for the survival of the places: the increased demand for goods and services through a qualified and specialized supply impact positively on the vitality and livability – increasing the satisfaction of residents and non-residents – on the profit performance of economic activities, the value of tangible place assets and general consent to governance.

IV. SERVICE PROVIDER NETWORKING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CITY ECONOMIES

Major territorial areas with a clear manufacturing identification, in the last years, have been skillful to rebalance the relationship between industrial settlement and dynamic development of service activities in the framework of economic and social offerings of a city or an area using sometimes the lever of events with media resonance extended to start the repositioning of an urban brand through continuous and capillary forms of communication to the stakeholders of this new identity.

Let’s consider, among others, the case of the city of Turin. Since at least a ten year period, with admirable foresight, it started to redeem the urban fabric and its external perceptions from the town-logo FIAT, (as it was for the mutatis mutandis of Termini Imerese) to go toward a new model of identity and a new image of place of culture, of advanced research, of knowledge, of film production, of entertainment, working on touristic and cultural co-marketing of an inter-city and an inter-regional nature. An example of this approach is MI TO, international review of events and cultural performances whose integrated fruition generates synergies and forms of collaboration and cooperation, even between cities and promotes tourist service based exchanges.

Turin is - de facto - a place brand that is prevalent in the Italian region of Piemonte. It represents the tangible example of the strategic foresight of all the players who worked very hard to the strategic redesign of their territory. They had a sharing of purposes with prevalent and obvious top-down choices in technological clusters and in innovation. This has been a winning action of territorial meta-management as all the economic, political, institutional and social components and also University studies and advanced Research have been involved in this place marketing.

These expertise, highly specific and qualified, were combined all together in a marketing plan pointed to change the perception of the identity of the place, to enhance a new one, to intensify relationships of interchange with cities-places-areas that have high planning capacity, to segment the “products and services” and to transmit knowledge of the new assets of the regional territory supplies identified in the historic-artistic heritage of the cities, in the number and the quality of research facilities, in the distinctive features of the locations bordering the county towns, in the town centers as containers of entrepreneurial of cultural

value, in the proximity of areas to be well known winter-like locations.

In the mere point of view of an academic who observes phenomena and deduces considerations and thoughts about it with the purpose of producing models, the Turin and Piemonte case, compared to the cases mentioned before, represents a best practice to be imitated as for predictive capability of context settings and as for new territorial format to be communicated to the market, even of the external investors.

After all the production companies seek, more and more, places and spaces, in these periods characterized by strong stagnation of demand in local environment in line with modern requirements for reducing the cost of the typical factors of production.

There are going to be several years of reconsideration of the territories, of the cities and in particular of the needs of those who live everyday in urban spaces, according to the new rhythms and needs. There will also be the an increasingly strong necessity of sociological and trading support and of assistance of services in general.

As already highlighted, the cities and in general the territorial areas are becoming organized and managed spaces (Minton, 2009 and Reeve, 1996); the economic trends cited are studied by the marketing and management reference, primarily through concepts related to public and private aggregations for the enhancement of quality of life and the optimization of the evolutionary process of the services and their service providers.

All over the world programs of control, of conservation and of urban re-generation have been designed and initiated, in view of the need of safeguarding the quality of life in the cities, of empowering the city users and of revitalizing urban areas according to new models. In the planning and management of the public and private sectors, many types of governance and especially of collaboration are being used.

Among them we recall the main tools of management and the organizations that have favored the network of service providers in the cities and contributed to limit the impact of the economic and employment crisis in urban areas spreading networks of knowledge and of models.

Many typologies of governance have been utilized in the planning and in the management of private and public sectors; particularly the main tools of management and the organizations have favored the network of service providers in the city and contributed to limit the impact of the economic and employment crisis in urban areas spreading networks of knowledge and of models: *National Main Street Programme* (USA), *Town Centre Management* (born and developed in UK), *Business Improvement District, Town Center Management place marketing organized* (Italy), *Società di Trasformazione Urbana* (STU); international organizations – for example *TOCEMA Europe*², *Institute of Place Management* and *London ATCM* – for the safeguard of the city centre.

² TOCEMA EUROPE is the European network of Town Centre Management (city centers) created within the framework of the European program INTERREG IIC. It is the result of extensive and diverse partnership of local, regional and state-controlled institutions such as national associations of Town Centre Management. It promotes initiatives of Town Centre Management across Europe and encourages the implementation of innovative projects for urban development. Its purpose is to create a European network for the Town Centre Management, which deals with issues of urban development such as trade, the urban environment (cleanliness, safety, livability, etc. ..), tourism, culture, accessibility, residence.

Also in England the tendency to value the service provider in the city is very strong. Over 600 coordinated management experiences of the redevelopment of the city from the perspective of management place between 1998 and 2006 and the activities have enhanced the services and related service providers.

Throughout Europe there is an ongoing process of reorganization of urban areas and in particular in urban areas according to evolving new principles and new demands of city users, investors, companies of different nature.

The governments of countries seek to protect the interests of economic development and sustainability-related in the light of a revolution in services, in advanced services, and the now recognized importance of group and social services for the city.

The contribution of Van den Berg (1990) through the key of the three levels of place marketing identifies the city as a product to be studied by parts and by homogeneous groups - different urban cluster - including, for example, the cluster retail as a synthesis of a homogeneous category of service providers, in some cities identified as Relevant Service Provider, and like driver of the economic revitalization of the urban⁵.

In the concept of place marketing on three levels clusters interact with each other defining the image of the place (in this case the city), because thanks to the interactions between the components, it conveys the place as a single "entity". The single entity values is greater than the value of the individual parts, in which, in certain cases, the retail acts as a economic development leve in a process of urban requalification.

Strategic marketing planning allows the actual development of the systemic interactions between the "places" in the city; therefore in advanced cases in which urban environments are deindustrialised necessarily economic development comes from the service industry and service providers. The task of the marketing strategy for the development of the territory is the systematization of the interactions between local stakeholders, for the identification of relevant service providers, which can contribute to the distinctive characterization of the place.

The place marketing management allow for strategic planning towards value creation and sustainable development in areas with strong relations between the local contest and service providers; some of them could be distinguished by efficiency and capacity by proving services to other stakeholders in different places, through knowledge, training and technology development.

In this sense the place management, converts the area into a productive servicescape in which the services are developed in view of "servuction" (Langeard, 1981) and emerge in parallel with relevant service providers capable of positioning the area and determine the development and value creation³.

The servuction model highlights the experiential aspects of purchases of goods and services by consumers, who will get the desired benefits through a service divided into visible elements – *environment within which the service experience occurs and the contact personnel of service providers who interact with the consumer during the service experience* - and invisible - *the performance explained at the time that you consume the service or experience, also characterized by the culture of the place* -.

³ It therefore creates a situation of mutual influence that stimulates one hand, the service providers to tend towards excellence, on the other territories to enhance the skills and knowledge generating internal value.

This means that the visible and tangible environment can significantly affect service provider and, therefore, the "places" - cities, stores, streets, shopping malls, various businesses, etc.. - contribute to offer the best possible service and at the same they are supported by the service provider - possibly through a place marketing strategy, creating the opportunity for the development of Relevant Service Provider -. It then generates the two-way relationship described in Figure 1.

The model has also found support in research of Warnaby and Davies (1997); the authors have highlighted the strong role of retail⁴ integrated in the city, understood in a holistic sense as suggested in the approach to development of the area proposed by Ashworth and Voogd (1990a and 1990b). The integration between the development strategies of each service provider, allow for definition of the place positioning. The expansion and growth of cultural and managerial skills allow to facilitate the assimilation of knowledge and complementary skills from the outside⁵ and to multiply the effects towards development.

V. AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF SERVICE PROVIDER IN PLACE MANAGEMENT

About subject that has been described above, the aim is to analyze some case studies in which it is possible to find the strategic role of service providers in the creation of clear and identifiable place positioning and image, the process that leads therefore to identify "the place" generating benefits for internal stakeholders and attracting many tourists. The de-materialization and the optimization of industrial processes, the crisis of employment in sectors with high level of industrialization and labor issues have led businesses to outsource and to divest plants and business structures (Levitt 1976; Heskett, 1986; Gershuny and Miles, 1983)

⁴ Some Authors (Moras et al, 2004) consider the retail - specific variation in the services industry - in the center of the design of urban redevelopment arguing, often rightly, that the need for integration in place planning is increasingly evident and, in an environment characterized by a very detailed legislation, local authorities should consider the need to integrate the development plans and redevelopment of the city - traffic plans, urban transport management, retraining programs and economic revitalization, tourism, security and recovery programs.

⁵ It is within the internal development of absorptive capacity (Cohen, Levinthal, 1990); the absorptive capacity is the ability of absorption or the ability to recognize the value, of appropriating and exploiting new knowledge or information.

The city of *Liverpool*, for example, in the years ' 70 underwent this phase of de-materializing both in the more central urban area – with the demise of several factories - and in the urban area of the port – with the port sector crisis due to technological developments and the advent of containerization-.

It is greatly reduced the demand for one type of labor and unemployment has increased. This reality has been configured as the real impetus for the redevelopment of the city towards services and knowledge.

It was studied new placements in the city according to service-oriented logic, through new legislation that favored public private initiative and the approach to "places" and to the territories in marketing optics.

In a long process of overall redevelopment, starting from the years ' 90, the city has been transformed and the public-private initiative has brought important results.

The city's skyline has changed and strategic commitment towards common development goals was shared by both private investors and the local government. - Liverpool was awarded the title of Capital Of Culture 2008- .

Among the significant initiatives that have enhanced the competitiveness of the city there is Liverpool ONE. Liverpool ONE is a project of urban renewal that has been the motor of economic development town by focusing on trade and services, engaging more than 920 million pounds.

The redevelopment project has revolutionized a vast territorial area of the city centre and encompassed management of streets and public squares according to agreements with the local government.

As evidence of the importance of service providers in the redevelopment of the sites we report the case of the recent "renewal" of Rome's Air Terminal Ostiense, generated by the intervention of private investors - Eataly and NTV-. The terminal Ostiense was born as one of the jewels of the World Cup in 1990 and was to be privileged even after the joint for the connection between the city and the airport of Fiumicino. However, since a few years it is the subject of a thorough and costly retraining, especially thanks to private initiative, which returns it to the city as a multipurpose facility.

The intense redevelopment began with the advent of NTV - *Nuovo Trasporto Viaggiatori*, an Italian railway undertaking operating in the field of high-speed rail. Later, in June 2012, the Rome's Air Terminal Ostiense also became the seat of Eataly Roma, which weaving catering, sales and teaching, art and food, allowed to redevelop an area in decline and at the same time to revive the strengths of 'national economy.

In favour of the whole area involved, the two Companies, while operating in different business areas, managed to give a high added value to a high number of stakeholders.

In particular, NTV and Eataly, for the entire urban area represent a major operation on employment, cultural and urban regeneration⁶, as well as a source of attraction for residents and for the number of tourists visiting Rome, but also for new business opportunities .

The space is also upgrading from the functional point of view due to the presence of "Casa Italo" NTV that, with its many services, can improve the quality of people's lives. Inside the building, the

⁶ The regeneration also occurs by an architectural point of view, since it involves existing buildings that have a high symbolic and cultural value to the city level.

perimeter architecture is designed as a wrapper collected and furnishing elements form circular islands where the traveler can enjoy a range of services. For over a decade the Ostiense⁷ area is a laboratory of urban development in which they were tested the original architectural and urban solutions. It has always been considered a strategic point for the modernization and transformation of the city for three main reasons: the extraordinary nature of the urban landscape, which is characterized by the presence of historically significant buildings such as the former Tobacco Factory, strong local identities as Garbatella, San Saba and Testaccio, high representation of buildings such as the University of Roma Tre, industrial areas disposed of in the course of transformation as the former slaughterhouse, the area Italgas and former Mercati Generali, and finally examples of industrial archeology and cultural goals such as the Teatro India and Montemartini.

Therefore, the presence of Eataly and Italo House represented the beginning of the renaissance of the Ostiense district. The spearhead of this revival is the Air Terminal that from an urban blight has become one of the most important centers of attraction in the city.

Due all of these elements Ostiense can be defined as the neighborhood with "the highest tone of a total transformation of Rome" to the benefit of its residents, tourists and the entire urban area.

Another relevant example is that of the "Trans-Siberian Railway in Italy", a disused railway that connects Sulmona-Carpinone, which was reopened for tourism purposes. In particular, the present project is the re-opening until Castel di Sangro, offering tourists the experience of traveling in space but also in time: the journey, made on board the carriages of the 20's, through the National Park of Majella and climbs up to Rivisondoli-Pescocostanzo, where there is the second highest railway station in Italy, after the Brennero. A path that winds through forests and beautiful landscapes, from the Majella and Gran Sasso, with a variety of climates and vegetation that have earned the Railroad Park the nickname of Trans-Siberian Railway in Italy. On the occasion of the transit of vintage trains along the line, are also organized several events in the stations cross, with a tasting of local products.

The sellout of the trips shows that the introduction of a given service, in this case also redeveloping disused structures, can be driver of an entire place area, and if this is supported through consistent marketing strategies, the place will have an image and a positioning such as to compete nationally and internationally.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion it is possible to highlight important managerial implications of this work, as it has proven as a place management planning consistent with the asset and shared by stakeholders, integrated with appropriate service providers, can generate a

⁷ Ostiense is the tenth district of Rome, the population of the urban area: 8266 inhabitants. The Ostiense is among the top 15 districts were born in 1911, officially established in 1921 and took its name from the neighborhood has seen Ostiense. It start your own urban development around 1907, when the Mayor Ernesto Nathan began to promote the creation of a industrial district at the beginning of the Via Ostiense. On this drive, and also because of the Master Plan of 1909, the Port River were built, the gasometer, the Montemartini and General Markets.

defensible competitive and long-lasting advantage, and let the place also compete at international level.

On the basis of significant results achieved by redevelopment project of Rome's Terminal Ostiense, it's possible to expect that analyzed case of "Trans-Siberian Railway" can represent an important opportunity and a starting point for revitalizing the entire area and it can create value for residents and tourists.

REFERENCES

- Ancarani, F., Valdani E. (2000) Strategie di marketing del territorio, Milano, Egea.
- Ashworth G.J., Voogd H. (1990) Selling the City. London: Belhaven
- Barthelemy, J. (2001) "The hidden costs of IT outsourcing". *Sloan Management Review*, 42, No. 3, 60-9
- Bastie J. e Dezert B. (1980) *L'espace urbain*, Masson, Parigi
- Baumol, W.J., (1967) "Macroeconomics of Unbalanced Growth: The Anatomy of Urban Crisis" *The American Economic Review*, Vol. 57, No. 3 pp. 415-426
- Baumol W.J. (2002) "Preface", in Gadrey J., Gallouj F. (eds.), *Productivity, Innovation and Knowledge in Services*, Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, UK Becattini G. (1998) *Distretti industriali e Made in Italy. Le basi socioculturali del nostro sviluppo economico*, Bollati Boringhieri, Torino
- Bell D., (1974) *The Coming of Post-Industrial Society*. Harper Colophon Books, New York
- Caroli M. G. (2006) *Il marketing territoriale. Strategie per la competitività sostenibile del territorio*, FrancoAngeli, Milano
- Coca-Stefaniak A., Quin S., Parker C. (2008) "European town centre management models and future challenges for the TCM profession", <http://www.placemanagement.org>
- Coca-Stefaniak A. (2008), "Place management is an interdisciplinary field"- *Journal of Place Management Volume 1 Issue 1* Publication, Emerald
- Cohen W. M., Levinthal D. A. (1990) "Absorptive Capacity: A New Perspective on Learning and Innovation", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, , Special Issue: Technology, Organizations, and Innovation., Vol. 35, No. 1 pp. 128-152.
- Gatti C., Schillaci C. E. (2011) "E pluribus unum: intenzionalità collettiva e governo dei sistemi territoriali" in *Sinergie* n.84
- Gattorna, J. (1998) *Strategic supply chain alignment: best practice in supply chain management*. Farnham: Gower Publishing
- Gershuny J. (1978) After industrial society?: The emerging self-service economy, Macmillan, London,
- Gershuny J., Miles I. (1983) The new service economy. The transformation of employment in industrial societies, Frances Pinter, London
- Gilodi C. (2004) Territorio e marketing, tra letteratura e nuovi percorsi di ricerca, Liuc Papers n. 149, Serie Economia e Istituzioni 13, Castellanza (VA)
- Goldfinger C. (1996) L'utile e il futile. Per un'economia dell'immateriale, Utet, Torino
- Grönroos, C. (1998) "New Competition in the Service Economy: The Five Rules of Service", *International Journal of Operations and Product Management*, Vol. 8 No.3, pp. 9-18.
- Grönroos, C. (1991) "The marketing strategy continuum: towards a marketing concept for the 1990s", *Management Decision*, Vol. 29, No. 1, p. 9.

- Gummeson, E. (1987) "The new marketing- Developing long-term interactive relationships". *Long Range Planning*. 20(4) (August): 10-20
- Heskett J., (1987) "Lessons in the service sector", *Harvard Business Review*, vol.2
- Levitt, T. (1976) "Industrialization of Services", *Harvard Business Review*, 54, 63-74
- Langeard, E. et Al. (1981) Marketing of Services: New Insights from Consumers and Managers, Report no. 81-104, Marketing Sciences Institute, Cambridge MA
- Martinelli F., Gadrey J., (2000) L'economia dei servizi , Il Mulino, Milano
- Minton A. (2006) The privatisation of public space. London: The Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors
- Minton A. (2009) Business Improvement Districts and innovative service delivery. School of Public Affairs, The City University of New York, The Price WaterhouseCoopers Endowment for the Business of Government
- Momigliano F., Siniscalco D. (1970) "Terziario totale e terziario per il sistema produttivo" in *Economia e politica industriale* n.25
- Moras G., Codato G., Franco E. (2004) L'approccio integrato alla qualificazione urbana. Modelli e strategie di urbanistica commerciale , CELID Torino
- Mclvor R. (2005) The outsourcing process: strategies for evaluation and Management. Cambridge University Press
- Parker C. (2008) "Extended editorial: place - the trinal frontier" *Journal of Place Management and Development*, Vol 1 No. 1, pp 5-14
- Parker, C. (2008) "Forthcoming articles in the Journal of Place Management and Development" Volume 1 Issue 1 Publication, Emerald, March
- Pencarelli T., Forlani F. (2002) "Il marketing dei distretti turistici - sistemi vitali nell'economia delle esperienze" in *Sinergie* n.58
- Quinn, J. B., Baruch, J., Paquette P.C. (2002) "Technology in Services". *Scientific American*, Vol. 257, No. 6, December, pp. 50-58.
- Reeve, A. (1996) The private realm of the managed town centre, *Urban Design International*, 1, 61-80.
- Rifkin, J. (2000) The age of access: the new culture of hypercapitalism, where all of life is a paid-for experience. J.P. Tarcher/Putnam, New York
- Rullani E. (1998) "Industriale e post-industriale: oltre il concetto di terziario" *Kibernetes*, n.19/20
- Rullani E. (1995) "Dematerializzazione" in: Caselli L. (a cura di) *Le parole dell'impresa. Guida alla lettura del cambiamento*, Eni-Isvet, Roma, 1995
- Rullani, E. (2002), Il distretto industriale come sistema adattivo complesso, in A. Quadrio Curzio e M. Fortis (2002) (a cura di), *complessità e distretti industriali. dinamiche, modelli, casi reali*, Il Mulino, Bologna
- Sahelman W.A., (1999) "The new economy is stronger than you think", in *Harvard Business Review*, Nov-Dec
- Stuart-Weeks, M. (1998) Place management: fad or future?, A presentation at the open forum, Institute of Public Administration Australia (NSW Division),
- Thurrow L.C., (1987) "La tecnologia dell'inefficienza", *Politica ed Economia*, n.9
- Van den Berg L., (1990) "Urban policy and market orientation", *Euricur*, Erasmus University Rotterdam, n. 4
- Van den Berg L., Braun E. (1999) "Urban competitiveness, marketing and the need for organizing capacity", in *Urban Studies*, Vol. 36
- Walsh, P. (2001) "Improving Government's response to local communities – Is place management an answer?", *Australian journal of Public Administration*, Vol 60, No 2.
- Warnaby, G. and Davies, B. J. (1997) Commentary: Cities as service factories? Using the servuction system for marketing cities as shopping destinations, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 25 (6), 204-210.